

Harmonic dualism: Analyses of musical works

This list provides an overview of a selection of analyses available in the sources from the annotated bibliography. They are group together with the source in which they can be found. A division is made between shorter fragments, that consist of only a few measures of music, and longer fragments. Each reference starts with the surname of the composer, followed by the piece that is analysed and ends with the person that did the analysis, as this is not always the author of the text. More detailed information on where exactly in the source an analysis can be found is always indicated in the source itself.

Byrne, D. A. (2018). *The Harmonic Theories of Sigfrid Karg-Elert: Acoustics, Function, Transformation, Perception* [Doctoral dissertation, University of Cincinnati]. OhioLINK Electronic Theses and Dissertations Center.

http://rave.ohiolink.edu/etdc/view?acc_num=ucin1522417315389199.

Longer fragments

- Beethoven, Sonata in C major, op. 53 ("Waldstein") - 1st movement. (By Karg-Elert)
- Liszt, "Wieder möcht' ich dir begegnen" (Lied, 1860) (By Karg-Elert)
- Schumann, Novelette in F major, op. 21 no. 1 (By Karg-Elert)
- Wagner, 'Schlafakkorde' from *Die Walküre* (Act III, scene 3) (By Karg-Elert)

Ergo, M. (1914). *Ueber Richard Wagner's Harmonik und Melodik. Ein Beitrag zur Wagnerschen Harmonik.* Breitkopf & Härtel.

Longer fragments

- Wagner, *Tannhäuser* overture (By Ergo)

Erpf, H. (1927). *Studien zur Harmonie- und Klangtechnik der neueren Musik.* Breitkopf und Härtel.

Short fragments

- Bruckner, 4th symphony, second movement (By Erpf)
- Mahler, 9th symphony, fourth movement (By Erpf)

Harrison, D. (1994). *Harmonic Function in Chromatic Music: A Renewed Dualist Theory and an Account of Its Precedents.* University of Chicago Press.

Short fragments

- Beethoven, Piano Sonata, op. 90, 1st movt. (By Riemann)
- Wagner, *Die Walküre*, act 3, scene 3. (By Karg-Elert)
- Wolf, *An den Schlaf*, segmental analysis of mm. 18-34. (By Harrison)

Longer fragments

- Frack, Pièce héroïque. (By Harrison)
- Reger, *Introduktion Passacaglia und Fuge.* (By Harrison)
- Mahler, Second Symphony, 5th movt. (By Harrison)

Karg-Elert, S. (1931). *Polaristische Klang- und Tonalitätslehre: (Harmonologik).* Indiana University.

Short fragments

- Karg-Elert, Dance-song from the 14th century with accompaniment by Karg-Elert. (By Karg-Elert)
- Wagner, "Tristan". (By Karg-Elert)

Klumpenhouwer, H. (2011). Harmonic Dualism as Historical and Structural Imperative. In *The Oxford Handbook of Neo-Riemannian Music Theories*, 194-218.

Longer fragments

- Beethoven, third movement from the Piano Sonata in A major, op. 101. (By Riemann)

Rehding, A. (2003). *Hugo Riemann and the Birth of Modern Musical Thought*. Cambridge University Press.

Short fragments

- Riemann, A Chinese 'Funeral March' in Riemann's harmonised setting from *Seth's original chinesische und japanische Melodien*. (By Rehding)
- Berlioz, *Benvenuto Cellini* (opening). (By Riemann)
- Beethoven, Sonata in F major, Op. 54. (By Riemann)
- Wagner, Tristan Prelude, mm. 8–11. (By Mayrberger)

Thomson, P. (2010). *Robert Mayrhofer's Theory of Harmony* [Unpublished master's thesis]. University of Alberta.

Short fragments

- Gottschalk, *Pensive*, mm. 1-14. (By Thomson)
- Schubert, *Valse noble No. 10*, D. 969 in F major. (By Thomson)
- Schumann, *Träumerei*, mm. 1-8. (By Thomson)
- Wagner, *Tannhäuser*, Pilgrims Chorus. (By Mayrhofer)

Tymoczko, D. (2011). Dualism and the beholder's eye. In *The Oxford Handbook of Neo-Riemannian Music Theories*, 246-270.:

Longer fragments

- Brahms, Op. 76, no. 4. (By Tymoczko)